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CORRUPTION AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC INEQUALITIES: A MARXIST CRITIQUE OF SUCCESS IN MOHSIN HAMID'S *HOW TO GET FILTHY RICH IN RISING ASIA* (2013)

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ABSTRACT

The current study aims to focus on the thematic framework of the novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* concerning corruption and socio-economic biasness through the critical examination of the transformation of self in order to get benefited in rapidly evolving socio-economic conditions. The novel traces the journey of an unnamed narrator whose personal ambition and societal structures both are marked by ethically ambiguous revenues. Use of second person narration symbolically depicts mutually shared hassles of the unprivileged groups particularly of rising Asia to navigate from being poverty-stricken to filthy rich in the face of capitalism. This study analyzes how characters present corruption as a byproduct and symptom of social and financial inequalities through their experiences. By employing Marxist Social Capital Theory and Patrimonial Capitalism theoretical lens, this paper argues that Hamid emphasizes the class distinction and exploitative dynamics as an outcome of corrupt corporate system acts as a catalyst for differentiation in urbanized Asian context. The protagonist's acceleration in novel's manipulative settings depicts duality of corruption as an enabler and thus a barrier. Therefore, as a result concentrated economies work as an allusion for real-world harsh realities. The current study provides insights into how literary texts can be used to analyze, expose and question the socio-economic structures. Hamid's use of satirical tone exposes striking reality of the society that dysfunctional institutions and lack of accountability, trap individuals in never ending cycle of corruption making it difficult to break these shackles of injustice.

Key Words: Corruption, Socio-economic, Inequalities, Filthy rich, Marxism, Social Capital, Patrimonial Capitalism, Urbanized Asia, Dysfunctional institutions

Introduction

Literature often serves as a mirror to reflect the societal expectations, morals, and ideologies of the societies. Mohsin Hamid, a renowned Pakistani author, explores the collective identities of the communities in the novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* (2013) through the symbolic portrayal by an unnamed narrator describing unprivileged groups' eagerness and aspiration to get rich even through filthy means. Corruption serving as the central theme of the novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*, highlights the fraudulent conduct of the individuals to meet societal and financial expectations. Through his evocative plot, he sheds light on the pressing issue that gaining through good ways has become a matter of convention and is substituted by exploitation. This research focuses on the ill ways explained in the novel through which one can prosper in this urbanized world by exploiting others. Mohsin Hamid puts socio-economic mobility parallel to deceit to showcase its never-ending relationship in developing countries. Hamid further cultivates the idea that due to the expansion in

population, enlargement of the rate of consumption and lack of resources, corruption is more of a necessity than a choice. He further satirizes the incompetent attitude of the institutions that lubricate the means to climb up the ladder of short-term goals. This research tends to explore dynamics of corruption that the informal networks not only inculcate social evils and moral decline, rather it has become a crucial tool for the survival and growth in rising Asia leading to the abusing of deprived groups. Present study explores coupled nature of corruption as a product similarly the driver of discrimination for attaining socio-economic advancements often disregarding morality and ethics. Through the experiences of characters of Hamid's novel, he portrays harsh realities of the necessitous group of rising Asia whose lives are always marked by the pressure to attain material success and compelling them to pursue illegal means, neglecting morality in a challenging environment. This study opts for the interdisciplinary approach by utilizing a qualitative approach with specific attention to textual and thematic analysis, dialogues, scholarly articles, book reviews, and ethical essays, combined with the Patrimonial Capitalism referring to a system where wealth is accumulated and inherited to next generations by power bearing elites. In addition to them, Marxism theory posits exploitation as a mere tool to reserve success within a flawed system and the protagonist's survival schemes expose socio-economic inequities which reveal that sustaining requires conformity to the crooked environment as well as ethical flexibility. Hence, Social Capital Theory states informal networking can grant individuals socio-economic favors that will be used to support analysis. Moreover, corruption while typically viewed as an immoral and illegal act can also serve as a facilitator to seek advancements in rising Asia. This research is significant because previous studies concentrated more on the detrimental impacts of corruption only a few focused on its duality that it rises and perpetuates through socio-economic disparity. This paper seeks to analyze corruption as an unconventional means of socio-economic mobility and it also represents how literary descriptions can supply social commentary providing valuable insights for the policy makers, practitioners and authoritative institutions to create legitimate pathways for attaining success making them feasible.

Objectives

- To analyze impacts of dysfunctional institutions in socio-economic dynamics through the lens of Mohsin Hamid's novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*.
- To investigate how the novel negotiates relationship of corruption and socio-economic disparities.

Research Questions

- How does Mohsin Hamid expose corruption as a product and driver of socio-economic prejudices in novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*?

- How does novel highlight the maladministration of the institutions triggering individuals to pursue illegitimate means?

Significance

The novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* provides rich narrative for present research that allows to delve into duality of the corruption in developing Asia as it can serve as an outcome and mediator of socio-economic subjugation depending upon one's class in social structure symbolically portrayed through the experiences of characters. This study not only examines corruption under the framework of wealth but it also has moral implications for socioeconomic stability fostering more just society. Current research analyzes the intersection between corruption and socio-economic conditions to expose systemic obstacles in sustaining growth and provides insight for authoritative institutions towards transparency and equity.

Delimitation of the Study

This study is delimited to Mohsin Hamid's novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*. His works often project human struggles and complexities to access socio-economic mobility. This novel is much suitable for this research because it captures the notion of fraudulence and socioeconomic prejudices, capitalism having thematic significance particularly within developing Asian context. This novel is specifically suited to the present study because experiences of the characters allude towards the contemporary social concerns. The analysis is delimited to exploration of corruption through textual evidences, sociological and economic literary theories both as catalyst and hurdle to attain socio-economic stability.

Literature Review

Corruption conventionally portrayed as a hurdle in attainability of democratic sturdiness and fair financial circulation it is also considered as a necessary evil to escape institutional delays. In Hamid's novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* Mohsin Hamid presents a narrative set within an under developing, socially and economically vibrant region. Hamid narrates socioeconomic conditions of the developing Asia through the lens of his unnamed narrator who showcases the symbiotic relationship of the exploitation and favorable outcomes through his journey from being down and out to a well-to-do person using questionable methods.

According to Carvajal (1999) corruption is a social pathology that is prolonged through the support of corporate networks hindering circulation of wealth and social equality causing inefficiency in society. Corruption refers to the abusive practice carried out by the authoritative institutions that paved the way for protagonist to navigate socio-economic structures. Characters of the novel often exploit system politically, socially, economically for personal gain. Protagonist rises his water business using shortcuts and connections. Water is treated as a commodity, often blurring

the ethical lines. Protagonist even being determined individual, he grays the moral expectations to gain magnificent profit, rationalizing ill activities as a vital part of doing business. Navarro, Shi (2001) states that social inequalities are the disproportions in education, public services, healthcare that arise from the intervention of political parties and the policies endorsing their interests. Social Inequalities informs about the unequal distribution of resources, opportunities, and liberty, prestige, recognition, and social acceptance one holds in community based on caste, race, gender, education, health, care. These social inequities are woven in the lives of the characters of the novel, shaping their destinies, ambitions, and social actions. Social status serves as a desire as well as obstacle. Narrator of the novel, having a poor rural background, strives and hopes to revive himself after moving to the city. Here he encounters multi-faceted realities of the urban life that not only being lush rich is enough, but one must have a certain lifestyle and choices so he opts for those choices to be socially acclaimed. Throughout his journey, he examines that the conformity to the living standards of the urbanized culture can make him climb the ladder of prosperity. So, he pressurizes himself and tries to reinvent himself in order to get fit in the elite circles often facing partialities. Social prejudices by Goldman (2001) refer to discrimination in healthcare, lifespan potential caused by indicators like interpersonal relations and socio-economic connections. It argues that health disparities are driven by societal associations caused by complex social structures.

Lin, Cook and Burt (2001) explore social capital which involves value of informal networking between individuals that provides resources like support in face of challenging environment, aiding professional, societal development and providing with the information. This research involves how social networking is assembled and in what ways it operates in society fostering partiality. Authors argue that social capital glues individuals to largest social systems but it can also impact socio-economic status leading to injustice. It plays vital role in attaining prosperity through dense relations but power dynamics also limit opportunities for other individuals. Thus, Hamid in his novel *How to get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* (2013) employs characters that metaphorically demonstrate social deviations like protagonist born to Poor household reflects how deprived ones often engage in illegal means to overcome societal fences, and the pretty girl love interest of the protagonist, her aspiration to escape her limited circumstances, drive her to adopt difficult choices in her career surpassing a society that commodifies charm and youth. Protagonist's family is a true depiction of people belonging to the lower class that are remained locked in the cage of poverty despite their inspirational hard work due to influential rivals of equality, specifically in developing Asian domains. Pande (2007) in his study, takes account of corruption through the framework of political and

socio-economic environment of developing and developed nations that in what way they are influenced by corruption which often stems from profitable decisions made by the political actors contributing towards higher level of disparities highlighting the potential of vulnerability towards interference of low-income nations. Vittal (2012) in his article, connects his idea of financial and social differentiation to Darwin's theory, survival of the fittest, indicates that human nature is inherently savage. One doesn't care about what transactions he is using to make himself worthy of appreciation in face of competitive environment. He further argues that humans are controlled by their instincts, often blinding other individuals' well-being and prioritizing one's own survival. Author focuses on the notion that lack of coherence in economic, intellectual, and social indicators result into widespread corruption. Rosenblatt (2012) using Social Dominance Theory presents the idea that individuals belonging to elite class have this illusion that they inherently belong to power and are entitled to exploit others to seek advancement and lower-status groups pass over corruption because sometimes they are the puppets of influentials or they try to fit in. Organizations help hiding corruption by incorporating policies and laws fostering power. The fusion of rationalized decisions and organizations preserve this social evil. Farooq, Shahbaz, Arouri and Teulon (2013) sheds light on investigation of corruption on economic grounds in Pakistan. Economic distortion could be defined as bias attitudes or practices reinforcing economic exclusion in terms of education, opportunities and wealth within a social setting. Corruption is a major threat that hinders growth of Pakistan due to unsupervised governance and eroding of public trust, but financial development and trading of openness can help to stimulate growth. Economic inequality is an umbrella term for multiple concerns regarding uneven distribution of income, accumulation of assets, unequal access to vital resources like education, employment, health facilities based on ethnicity, and social class.

Mohsin intricately depicts differences through the lives and situations of characters installed in the novel mainly protagonist's tangy circumstances from being a rural boy to filthy rich explains the struggles of privileged groups. Despite achieving immense wealth his stance in aristocratic society remains fragile which criticizes accumulation of wealth in few hands leading to generational inequity. Majewska (2013) states that association between corruption and social capital development denotes that how corruption obstructs the productivity socially and financially inculcating weakening social welfare. Corruption erodes public trust, fairness and cooperation in public systems. This study uses data from organization like World Bank which shows that countries with less corruption rate tend to excel more than the ones with higher proportion due to low public interests and more personal agenda. Majewska advocates for the quality governance and just

laws for eliminating injustice in any society.

Coetzee (2014) in his article, deals with the matter of corruption that it is not just matter of nobility rather a disruption in governance and establishment of healthy markets affecting the stability and ability of institutions in fostering processes. It further emphasizes on the suffrage of vulnerable groups that corrupt practices deepen inequalities and worsen poverty. Awan (2017) states that the social critique of Hamid's novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* explores social evils of South Asia by symbolically employing second-person narration, "you", in order to reflect the systematic inequalities in Asian context. Researchers underline the prime issues such as unemployment, terrorism, corruption, class distinction, nepotism, and unchecked bureaucracy persuading individuals to ascend the socioeconomic pyramid through unethical means in order to escape poverty. Amin (2018) investigates the impact of corruption on socio-economic blooming in South Asia. Major findings of this article indicate the adverse impacts of corruption on the socio-economic indicators like limiting financial growth, faulty public services like education and health. Exploitation in education sectors result in higher illiteracy rate and reduced future manpower quality. While in health maintenance it inculcates into worst health outcomes due to recruitment of unqualified professionals leading to expansion of mortality rate. It also encourages the concept of bribery for getting enrolled in any educational institution which reduces merit-based admissions. Spyromitros and Panagiotidis (2022) propose that corruption generally seizes the growth in marginalized countries but its effect can vary. In some regions, corruption might serve as a facilitator of gaining advancements in the face of adversity depending on the governance and administrative quality on the other hand it can harm development by limiting efficiency, clarity and deteriorating institutional performances. Saleem, Raza, Baloch and Abro (2024) examine the issue of class discrimination through a Marxist lens, revealing the scarcity of opportunities due to the impact of socio-economic inequalities. It highlights the fact that local educational and poor rural background limits your access to build up money, which automatically pushes individuals to pursue crime and illegitimate means to seek better life. Socio-economic tussles lead to the notable hardships for the developing class. Besides class struggle this research also emphasizes on the social evils like unemployment, limited attention to healthcare, quality education due to unequal distribution that emerged in marginalized groups.

Higgins (2024) discusses that when the wealth is accumulated in elite individuals and passed down to the next generations, it results in persistent socio-economic injustice. The researcher further critiques that such concentration of wealth not only shapes authoritative structures but is also compounded by the widening of gendered and racial inequalities, reinforcing domination over

unprivileged groups. Hamid's novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* blends themes of socio-economic prejudices with corruption stating that it is not only failing of single individual rather associative collapse of social system. The dominance of corrupt elite class over social and economic spheres as our protagonist faced during his struggling phase and he himself became that barrier which projects the turmoil of marginalized sector also corruption acting as an impediment and catalyst to ascend the pyramid of stability.

Research Gap

Despite there is a considerable amount of literature exploring corruption but only few studies emphasized on the notion of intersection between corruption and socio-economic discrimination particularly regarding Asian context. Most studies tend to aim corruption as a stand-alone evil with lack of literary focus without exploring its duality as an ingredient and product paralyzing social mobility. There are further aspects that can be explored like how discrimination impacts marginalized gendered dynamics and the comparative study with contemporary texts concerning issues to identify literary variations.

Methodology

Present study settles on comprehensive methodology for the critical analysis of corruption and socio-economic prejudices in Hamid's novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*. The research opts for the qualitative method involving detailed analysis of the text, characters, symbolic themes, and narrative techniques which permits for exploration of notion of corruption and differentiation are either depicted or critiqued. This study uses Marxist, Social Capital Theory and Patrimonial Capitalism theoretical framework to critically analyze class struggle, concentration of wealth, power dynamics and commodification of relationships and morality. This study utilizes text of the novel as primary data source having focal attention to chapters, passages, textual lines and characters' interaction to socio-economic systems. It involves the key examination of imagery, symbolism and figurative techniques presenting the dilemmas of the characters associated to inequalities. Scholarly articles, critical essays, books, journals offer as a secondary data source for the analysis. The aim of this study is to uncover the channels through which corruption acts as a dual-edged sword, as a driver and product of structural flaws, contextualizing vast social and economic discourses. The methodology balances the textual evidences, thematic and theoretical framework for critical analysis that aligns with the objectives of the study.

Theoretical Framework

Marxism provides a significant lens to observe the contemporary socio-economic and political landscapes. The root concepts of Marxism like capitalism, materialism, class struggle and quest for resources provide relevance to analyzing of modern societal

structure. According to Lenin (1995) Marxism is a social development theory that expresses the necessity of overthrowing of capitalists and taking over of the proletariats' leading classless society. Vladimir Lenin's contribution to the Marxism theory could be underlined by focusing on the Marxism (Leninism) that highlights the transformative approaches in backward societies. He is of view that there must be a vision-bearing party to lead the under developing groups. He also stressed upon the lingering impact of imperialism and state producing oppression and suppression. He argues for the unauthorizing of the state with a dictatorship of the proletariat to prevail communism. He states imperialism as the topmost stage of profit-oriented system. Lenin views corruption as a product of imperialist ideology, where the system and organization both collides with the ethical parameters inculcating domestic labor and further exploitation oppressing interests of the dominant elite class.

Wolff (2013) presents the contrast between the traditional Marxism and the over-determinist Marxism, offering the altered opinions regarding the aims of these anti-capitalist approaches. Over-determinist reinforces the idea of eradication of class exploitation by reordering the distribution of abundant labor and production, contrary to the conventional Marxism stating abolishing corporate ownership. S. Amin's study (2018) is the extended version of the Marx concept of the unpaid labor, where the workers are forced to do abnormal labor and with low wages, skimming profits from them. Amin further analyzes this concept under the umbrella of the global capitalism, another concept of the imperialist rent, which refers to how corporate institutions extract significant labor equivalent to the global north, but comparatively less profit is awarded to the global south, which projects structural discrimination between the nations. He criticizes the concept of the dominant corporation, controlling production, amount of labor, reward, and resource circulation. He also states that modern capitalism significantly involves monopoly of finance capital, which results in dominance of global north and rises sensitivity towards the global south. His contributions provide insights to look at the notion that global capitalism enriches few and traps large marginalized groups into never-ending circle of poverty. Engels (2019) in Communist Manifesto underlines the theory of historical materialism. He found the evolution of societal structures from communal society to patriarchal systems. He sheds light on the family dynamics and the kinship changed from the matriarchal to the men-centered communities. Engels further argues that initially women hold higher rank but with the passage of time, as the men gained social stability and fashion of private property emerged, it led to the subjugation of the women. This shift pushed women to pursue secondary roles as domestic workers, creating socio-economic disparities for them. Engels states that introduction of personal estates and enlargement of the families led to the

accumulation of the wealth in few hands inculcating generational oppression. In the Communist Manifesto to Karl Marx and Engels posits that the evolution of the humans is marked by the class struggle and they both argue that capitalist societies are driven by the tussle between the bourgeois and pro-literate class. The manifesto calls for the overthrowing of the elite class and creating classless society. Marx and Engels proposed that specific measures could be taken to overcome capitalist state by the imposition of taxation, cost-free education and prohibition of the concentration of wealth. The Communist Manifesto is one of the crucial segment of the Marxism advocating for the reformative social change. Marx and Engels both were of the opinion that corporate systems are innately exploitative in nature and also by criticizing the role of state acting as a mediator for fulfilling the agendas of the dominant class. Wu (2024) Marxism is a socio-economic theory that criticizes capitalist perception and reinforces the human non-conformity and social liberation. In accordance to Karl Marx, concept of anti-poverty theory eliminates capitalism's exploitative nature and accumulation of the wealth by corporate relations, is the central to the social issues like poverty and corrupt practices. Thus, he favors the eradication of capitalist structures for fostering productivity and lower-class consciousness to conquer liberty and to dig out the causes of poverty at a broader level. Marx further argues for the need of the proletariat to give awareness that capitalists create economic crisis by compiling it to self and accelerating the struggle for lower class. He also offers a systematic approach that is grounded in the history for narrating inflation, providing manual book for the contemporary society towards limiting labor and increase human liberty and development.

Data Analysis

Mohsin Hamid (2013) is often recognized for his exploration of themes related to the aftermath of corruption and its after effects on the individuals and societies. He skillfully incorporates characterization, thematic choices and figurative techniques negotiating multiple concerns regarding power dynamics. Hamid's works often contain social commentary addressing the consequences of inequalities especially in marginalized groups. His novel *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* delves into the consequences of corruption and resilience of human spirit in the face of it. Author skillfully employs compelling storytelling to define the internal struggles of the characters connecting their personal experiences to broader context of society.

Your teacher did not want to be a teacher. He wanted to be a meter reader at the electric utility. Meter readers do not have to put up with children, work comparatively little, and what is more important, have greater opportunity for corruption, and are hence both better off and held in higher regard by society (Hamid, 2013; p.19).

Hamid's ironical tone reflects a society where materialistic gain is more preferred rather than well-being of others. Teacher is conventionally allusion for guidance, knowledge divinity, ethical mentor and the one with higher regard. But in present times teaching is also associated with the profession driven by materialistic pursuits. Novelist not only critiques the fragmented minds of contemporary societies but also reveals the real agenda of corrupt skulls by highlighting the erosion of moral values. Profession of meter reading is considered more preferable because it allows the access towards the fat informal opportunities with less or no effort or gained through bribery or manipulation. Hamid reveals that corruption is not only tolerated in contemporary Asia but it also acts as an inspiration to get success. Author deals with the commodification of toil that even though teaching requires abundant efforts and teachers endure higher work load but awarded less in comparison to meter readers whose work is much easier as well as chances of getting riches are more through filthy means. Novel presents the striking reality of society that meter reading paradoxically ascend the social status creating biasness that focuses more corrupt practices over ethical concerns. The phrase "meter reader" symbolically projects the shared ideology of the people regarding normalizing of corruption as a survival strategy.

Because if you truly want to become filthy rich in rising Asia, as we appear to have established that you do, then sooner or later, you must work for yourself. The fruits of labor are delicious, but individually, they're not particularly fattening. So don't share yours, and munch on those of others whenever you can (Hamid, 2013; p.60).

The use of second person narration "You" offers as a satire to individualistic ideals that desire for personal gain and exploitative mindset is vital to navigate the capitalist society. Novel's cynical tone hints towards the prioritizing of self over others. The use of metaphor "Fruit of labor" suggests gain earned through hard work but in the following line author also ironically states to "munch on those of others" which suggests the idea that striving is fine but manipulating and exploiting others is the fastest way to excel. Novel offers pragmatic tone yet morally ambivalent exposing the lust for wealth and selfishness. Author's employment of satirical self- help format illustrates the moral compromises one has to make in order to thrive in this predatory environment. By emphasizing on the need of self-reliance and endorsement of corruption over collective welfare clarifies the unfortunate idea of selfishness as immediate reward winning mechanism. The voice of the novel is suggestive and sarcastic referring to the absurdity that either subjugating others is a necessary evil to survive or it is due to the outcome of corruption.

You were delivered to him by sticky web of red tape. Permits denied, inspections failed, meters improperly read, audits initiated, all these

scams and hassles you have over the years surmounted by greasing junior and mid-level palms. But you have reached an impasse (Hamid, 2013; p.85).

This textual line critiques the bureaucratic system and corruption stemming from it. The metaphorical use of the phrase “sticky web of red tape” alludes towards the spider’s web that indicates its complexity, obstruction, confinement and filth difficult to escape from. It emphasizes on the corrupt acts practiced by authorities labelled for providing justice are perpetuating systemic exploitation. Furthermore, author’s cataloging “permits denied, inspections failed, meters improperly read, audits initiated” denotes the challenges, restrictions and ever-consuming nature of corruption in a way to prosperity. Phrase “greasing junior and mid-level palms” is a symbolism to abuse of authority by practicing extortion and bribery which act as an agent for fueling oppressive systems. Tone of the text is realistic which reflects the draining journey of protagonist where corruption is normalized and also acts as a survival scheme. These paradoxical chunks “have over the years surmounted by greasing junior and midlevel palms” and “reached an impasse” indicates the juxtaposed idea that even after immense moral compromise one is unable to meet his requirements indicating persistent socio-economic injustice.

Your costs are low because your master sources recently expired goods at scrap prices, erases the expiry date from the packaging, and reprints a later date instead (Hamid, 2013; p.58).

This quotation presents the stance of society that economic instability blinds the ethical boundaries often compromising consumer’s safety over personal agenda. The practice of revising expiry dates reflects the desire to have more using deceitful methods regulated in competitive capitalist society in order to survive. The phrase “costs are low” is paradoxical term stating that in rising Asia your business can thrive only if your investment is low and cost of others is high.

Use of metaphor “erases the expiry date from the packaging” serves for the diminishing accountability and concealing of factual evidences. Vivid description of “expired goods” connotes the ethical degeneration and manipulation of truth. The competitive environment slides individuals towards the dehumanizing behaviors. It provokes the reader to interrogate the societal expectations regarding earning profit in cost of consumer’s safety.

His wife, the pretty girl's mother, suffers from severe and premature arthritis, a condition that makes her work as a sweeprress, the only work she could find when circumstance thrust her relatively late in life into the paid labor force, an exercise in unmitigated agony (Hamid, 2013; p.35).

The quotation revolves around themes of sufferings, stereotypical gender roles, complexities of human experiences in challenging societal norms. To portray the true image of the society

Hamid paints the picture of physical as well as psychological toil of subjugated communities. The narration satirizes the incompetency of system that pretty girl's mother was forced to do labor despite of having physical inability to make both ends meet. The wife's "premature arthritis" refers to her physical ailment as well as metaphorical for her premature wearing of her youth in face of adverse circumstances. Her job as a sweepress indicates the contracted opportunities for the women especially from oppressed socio-economic classes forcing them to use physical strength and to do underpaid work. The "an exercise in unmitigated agony" is a metaphor to her never-ending trails and tolls from which her body and spirit regularly suffers. Juxtaposition in her identity as mother of pretty girl and a sweepress creates a height of identity crisis in economic hardships. This line presents the concern of biasness in economic constraints that pushes women to offer hardships.

In the coming months, your mother's suffering is extreme, her cancer having metastasized to her bones and lungs. Her death, in the absence of modern palliative care is preceded by agony, only partially mitigated in her final fortnight (Hamid, 2013; p.47).

This quotation captures the inadequate healthcare facilities and miseries tolerated by unprivileged groups. It reflects the theme of familial dynamics, complexities, agony and failing of systemic structures. Firstly, the poor health condition and secondly death of protagonist's mother due to economic instability and lack of access to modern facilities is a mirror to socio-economic stratification. Cancer is a token for parasite that engulfs individuals not only through physical ailment but it is also a symbol of mental suffrage due to socio-economic divisions. Impaired concentration of medical care stamped for inevitability of her death like others belonging to lower class trapped in cyclic nature of poverty. By employing sorrowful tone novelist evokes compassion among readers that emphasizes the severity. Juxtaposition of modern palliative and its absence in her medical care exhibits the notion that health facility is a privilege rather than an innate right. Vivid imagery of her death "in her final fortnight" projects her decay and mortality but at the same time redemption that her life is now out of imprisonment imposed by social cage.

Your teacher's tone is soft with Menace. "Why did you say that?" "Twelve twelves are a hundred forty-four." "You think I am an idiot?" "No, sir. I thought you said a hundred thirty-four. I made a mistake. You said a hundred forty-four. I'm sorry, sir." The entire class knows your teacher did not say a hundred forty-four. Or perhaps not the entire class (Hamid, 2013; pp.18, 19).

The choice of diction exhibits colloquial expressions rich in rising Asian context. It involves the exploration of power dynamics, subjectivity of truth, misconception and coercive tactics. Metaphorical description of "soft with menace" describes two parallel concepts of calmness and fear-mongering provides the cognitive dominant move. The conversation between protagonist

and his teacher denotes shared roles appointed by society that student must conform to his teacher either right or wrong because he is mighty in every regard. Student's tone reflects his subjugated and self-defensive mood in contrast to unequal power. By the corrupt use of power teacher incorporates doubts through drilling instead of clearing concepts about facts. The fragmented perception evident from "perhaps not the entire class" shadows the collective internal struggle and identity crisis of marginalized groups. It provides evidence of fragility in front of exploitative powers.

A small payment and exam invigilators are willing to overlook neighborly cheating. More and someone else can be sat in your seat to write your paper. More still and no writing is needed, blank exam books becoming, miraculously, a first-class result (Hamid, 2013; pp.39, 40).

The textual evidence indicates the normalization of corruption in educational institutes which is the systemic failure of the authoritative institutions leading to the ethical degradation. It also indicates the devaluing of the merit that the ones having magnanimous amount of wealth can afford to access all the fruitful opportunities and the ones having no access tends to face the societal discrimination. The usage of bribery in achieving higher grades leads to the lowering of transaction for the people with intellect from achieving academic success. It serves as a social commentary of the developing nations that success is a game of wealthy individuals and the absurdity of "blank exam books" and "a first-class result" indicates the hollowness of the one.

Your city is not laid out as a single-celled organism, with a wealthy nucleus surrounded by an ooze of slums. It also lacks since the end of colonization generations ago, governance powerful enough to dispossess individuals of their property in sufficient numbers. Wealthy neighbor-hoods are often divided by single boulevard from factories and markets and the graveyards, and those in turn may be separated from the homes of the impoverished only by an open sewer, railroad track, or narrow alley (Hamid, 2013; pp.17, 18).

This passage represents the protagonist in land migration with his family from rural area to urban area, where there are restrictions regarding living standards, lower class people are separated with the barriers and their landscapes involve sewers and railroads which indicates their exile from the society which is dominant. The class division indicates the lingering impacts of the colonialism on the minds of the colonized nations, which are under-developing. The phrase, single cellular organism, explains the city as an organized and systematic where there is no interconnectedness like rural areas. The oxymoron of single-celled organism, which depicts the chaos versus order, that city is a well-organized and well-mannered place to live, but at the same time it is mentally chaotic and hectic often resisting emotional

connectedness.

Your organization is, like all organizations, an economic enterprise. The product it sells is power. No, you are part of something larger, something righteous. Something that is, if called upon to be, utterly ferocious (Hamid, 2013; pp.40, 41).

This textual evidence provides the duality of the organization, firstly presenting themselves in a disguise to help people thrive, and on the other hand promoting aggressive notions in order to meet their personal interests. It also metaphorically states “something larger, utterly ferocious” that something right and aggressiveness both are put in contrast to showcase its never-ending relationship while excelling in rising Asia. The author also highlights the tension between the moral ambiguity and sense of purpose in cities where violence is prime to present authority. It states that organizations provide a sense of belonging as well as treat the people coming from the lower background as a commodity by making them agree to use the aggressive behaviors.

Findings

After the critical analysis of the novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*, which is a satirical narration, the findings of the research include that, in accordance to the novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*, the corruption is an inevitable necessary evil. Hamid's protagonist was not innately involved in the corrupt practices but became a product of the illegitimate environment. Portrayal of the all characters involved in illicit practices have faced socio-economic subjugation. Hamid mocks the myth of hard work and underlines the importance of corporate connections as a survival strategy. Protagonist's and pretty girl's journey in the pursuit of wealth indicates the sense of loss of self and familial bondage. The interconnectedness of corruption and socio-economic growth prevails injustice because it clogs the ways to access resources without facing societal divisions. This novel is an oxymoron to self-help book criticizing the ideals of flourishment in rising Asia providing a healthy discourse to raise awareness about the perpetuating issue of corruption and it also highlights the need for reforms to tackle the generational social issues.

Conclusion

In the novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*, Mohsin Hamid (2013) explores the theme of corruption and socio-economic inequality by painting a picture of modernizing and the contemporary capitalist-minded society in rapidly developing Asia. Corruption serves as both product and driver for the success of often-perpetuating inequalities. Through the depiction of the unhealthy experiences of the characters, Hamid satirizes the moral ambiguity and normalization of the corruption to excess prosperity. Socio-economic disparities act as an opportunity for wealth-bearing groups as well as the hindrance for poverty marked mass. Corruption acts as an opportunity to navigate the bureaucratic systems easily with the corporate connections and informal

relationships, often marginalizing the commodification of the labor of the marginalized group in order to fuel the dreams of the elite class. Hamid's novel, *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia*, attracts the broader implication of the topic that in rapidly modernizing and urbanizing time. The exploitation is persistent in all institutions, resulting into pressing the inevitably of corruption. The novel provides a lens for the authorized beings to address and take measures to eradicate these social stigmas.

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